

Sulphur Elimination from Iron Pyrite by Methanol

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Sulphur elimination from natural iron pyrite (95.19 pyrite and 4.63% silica) from Amjhore, Bihar as well as synthetic iron pyrite with methanol has been studied in a fixed-bed tubular reactor in the range of 300-550° and 340-550°, respectively with the objective of developing a process for the elimination of sulphur. The effect of various process variables has been studied. 57.7% sulphur could be eliminated from natural iron pyrite under the optimum conditions.

EFFICIENT recovery of sulphur from natural sulphide minerals has led to extensive research for developing new methods especially in countries lacking deposits of brimstone. Much work has been done on the elimination of sulphur from iron pyrite which is abundantly distributed in nature. Roasting of iron pyrite in air at high temperature has been carried out earlier¹⁻³.

India has large deposits of iron pyrite in Amjhore, Bihar. Though Amjhore pyrite ore has been exploited for recovery of sulphur by thermal decomposition^{4,5} and other methods^{6,7} no systematic study had been done on the reaction of iron pyrite with organic compounds prior to the one reported by the authors on the reaction of both natural and synthetic iron pyrite with ethanol⁸, wherein 54.5% sulphur had been eliminated under the optimum conditions and the solid residue was found to contain FeS, 79.03; Fe₂O₃, 11.62; unreacted FeS₂, 5.6; and silica, 3.75%.

This study of the reaction of methanol with natural iron pyrite obtained from Amjhore, Bihar and synthetic iron pyrite prepared in our laboratory was conducted to see whether the reaction of methanol with iron pyrite increases or decreases the elimination of sulphur from pyrite. Hence, an attempt was made to investigate the feasibility of elimination of sulphur from both natural and synthetic iron pyrites by treating them with methanol. The detailed study on the influences of different process variables, like particle size, space velocity, temperature, partial pressure of methanol vapour and reaction period, on the elimination of sulphur was pursued to develop a process for the elimination of sulphur from natural iron pyrite. The effect of different additives on this interaction was also studied. This reaction has been studied in the temperature range 300-550° with natural iron pyrite. The reaction was also studied with synthetic iron pyrite to avoid the effect of contaminations associa-

ted with natural iron pyrite and was studied in the temperature range 340-450°.

Experimental

The reaction of iron pyrite with methanol was studied by following the procedure developed by the authors for the reaction of iron pyrite with ethanol⁸. The composition of samples of different particle size of the natural iron pyrite ore supplied by Pyrites Phosphates and Chemicals Limited, Amjhore after proper treatment was, -100+120 B. S. mesh (Fe, 44.32; S, 50.88; SiO₂, 4.63%), -120+150 B. S. mesh (Fe, 45.23; S, 51.87; SiO₂, 2.78%), and -150+170 B. S. mesh (Fe, 45.23; S, 51.90; SiO₂, 2.65%). Synthetic iron pyrite was prepared by following the procedure given in the reaction of iron pyrite with ethanol⁸.

The composition of the solid residue left after the reaction and the extent of sulphur elimination was determined by the reported procedure⁸. Solid products were also confirmed by X-ray diffraction. Hydrogen sulphide was found as one of the gaseous effluents. Other compounds present in the effluent could not be identified due to a complicated mixture of thiols, sulphides and polysulphides as indicated by chemical tests⁹ and mass spectra of different fractions obtained by the fractional distillation of the condensates.

Results and Discussion

The effect of various process variables on sulphur elimination was studied separately on natural and synthetic iron pyrite as per details given below.

Sulphur elimination from natural iron pyrite: There was very little effect of particle size as well as flow rate of methanol vapour. Elimination of sulphur increased from 10.82 to 12.34% by decreasing the particle size from -100+120 to -150+170

B. S. mesh at 400°. Increasing the flow rate from 8.5 to 51.9 l h⁻¹ resulted in the decrease of sulphur elimination from 14.05 to 9.02%.

To study the effect of space velocity, bed volume of iron pyrite was changed while the flow rate was kept constant as 34.6 l h⁻¹. The increase from 3.46 × 10⁴ to 6.92 × 10⁴ cc cc⁻¹ h⁻¹ resulted in increasing sulphur elimination from 36.83 to 46.10% at 450° (Fig. 1). This was perhaps due to the easy release of gaseous or low boiling products from the

Fig. 1. Effect of space velocity.

reaction sphere due to the high flow rate of methanol vapour. The same observation has been reported earlier in the reaction of pyrite with ethanol⁸ and in the reaction of pyrite with other compounds^{6,10}.

The increase in temperature from 400 to 550° resulted in an increase of about 43% sulphur elimination from 12.81 to 55.87%. The effect of reaction period was studied at intervals of 5, 10, 15, 30 and 45 min at temperatures 450, 500 and 550° and the results are graphically shown in Fig. 2. The elimination of sulphur increased from 9.79 to 45.64% in 5 min on increasing the temperature from 450 to 550° and

Fig. 2. Effect of reaction period (natural iron pyrite).

to 54.39% in 15 min. On further increasing the reaction period from 15 to 45 min no appreciable change was noted. One important observation is that the amount of Fe₂O₃ increased on increasing the reaction period. The composition of the solid residue at 550° in 15 min reaction period was found to be, unconverted FeS₂, 7.88; FeS, 75.42; Fe₂O₃, 12.98; and silica, 3.73%.

The effect of partial pressure was studied at 450° using three partial pressures of methanol

vapour, *i.e.* 0.2, 0.5 and 1.0 atm. The effect of partial pressure at 0.75 atm could not be studied due to back-suction of methanol vapour, the pressure of carrier gas N₂ being lesser than the methanol vapour. Sulphur elimination increased from 10.82 to 15.82% in 10 min and from 40.52 to 49.59% in 45 min on increasing the partial pressure from 0.2 to 0.5 atm. However, no increase in sulphur elimination could be observed by increasing the partial pressure from 0.5 to 1.0 atm as reported earlier in the reaction of iron pyrite with ethanol⁸.

While studying the effect of additives, it was observed that addition of ferric oxide decreased sulphur elimination from 49.37 to 36.04%, and MnO₂ to 44.25%. Vanadium pentoxide, silica and hydrogen sulphide did not affect the process of sulphur elimination.

Sulphur elimination from synthetic iron pyrite: The effect of particle size, flow rate, space velocity and partial pressure of methanol vapour was found to be the same as in the case of reaction with natural iron pyrite. However, while studying the effect of temperature and reaction period, sulphur elimination was found to increase with synthetic iron pyrite at comparatively lower temperatures under the similar experimental conditions. Sulphur elimination increased from 15.65 to 54.29% on increasing the temperature from 340 to 500°, whereas only 49.33% sulphur was eliminated from natural pyrite at 500° in 30 min. The effect of temperature on sulphur elimination, both from natural and synthetic iron pyrite is graphically represented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Effect of reaction period (synthetic iron pyrite).

The effect of reaction period was studied at four temperatures, *viz.* 340, 375, 400 and 450°. Sulphur elimination did not show much upward trend beyond 450° where 53.2% sulphur was eliminated in 30 min. Pyrite conversion also increased with the increase in reaction period at different temperatures. Fractional conversion of the order of 0.52 was found to occur at 340° in 75 min and which rose to 0.91 at

375° during the same reaction period. At 450° it reached to 0.54 in 5 min and increased to 0.93 within 10 min. These results are graphically presented in Fig. 4. The pyrite conversion was found to be 0.52 in case of methanol and 0.82 for ethanol.

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature.

Keeping in view the above results of the effects of various process variables, optimum conditions were established for maximum elimination of sulphur. As the decrease of particle size was not found to increase the sulphur elimination to an appreciable extent, the particle size of $-120+150$ B. S. mesh was chosen as the optimum. Increase in temperature enhanced sulphur elimination. Temperature of 550° was found to be most favourable because further increase of temperature resulted in thermal decomposition of the pyrite. The increase in sulphur elimination was not found beyond 15 min

at 550°, so 15 min was chosen as optimum reaction period. Increase in space velocity from 4.613×10^4 to 6.92×10^4 cc cc⁻¹ h⁻¹ increased the sulphur elimination by 2%, so the latter was taken as the limit. The partial pressure of 0.5 atm was taken as optimum because further increase in pressure of methanol vapour to 1.0 atm increased sulphur elimination by 1-2% for different reaction periods. Under these conditions, 57.7% sulphur could be eliminated from natural iron pyrite. The product distribution of the solid residue under these conditions was, FeS, 72.92; Fe₂O₃, 17.42; Unreacted FeS₂, 5.82; and silica, 3.84%.

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